

Family as a Central Metaphor in the Poetry of A.K. Ramanujan's *Relations*

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Abstract:

A. K. Ramanujan, a trilingual writer with equal mastery over English, Tamil and Kannada, preferred English for his creative writings, i.e. poetry. His themes concerned his experiences of first thirty years in India, his frequent visits field trips and his personal and professional preoccupation with Kannada, Tamil, the classics and folklore. His collection, 'Relations' contains these themes exploring his various relations to Religion, Family, Society, Nature, and Foreign Land. Family is the central metaphor he uses in almost all of his poems. The relations in a family such as father, mother, husband- wife, kith and kin are focused. He expresses his deep love for his mother and estrangement with his father. The relation in husband-wife is like Ardhnari Nateswara in Indian culture. Further, the broken relationship with his wife is he thinks, because of their 'unshared childhood.' He also compares the family system in India and U.S. A. In Indian family system there is United Family which accommodates all the relations under one roof. He is also a loving father for his daughter.

The researcher tries to explore different family relations used as a central metaphor in his poetry collection, 'Relations'.

Keywords: Family, United Indian Family, Ardhnari Nateswara, Central Metaphor.

Introduction:

A. K. Ramanujan, a trilingual writer with equal mastery over English, Tamil and Kannada, preferred English for his creative writings, i.e. poetry. His themes concerned his experiences of first thirty years in India, his frequent visits field trips and his personal and professional preoccupation with Kannada, Tamil, the classics and folklore. His Relations contains some of his poems of these themes exploring his various relations to Religion, Family, Society, Nature, and Foreign Land. According to a noted Indo Anglican poet R. Parthasarathy, "family is one of the central metaphors with he thinks." (The Literary Criterion, 1976, pp. 190) As K. R. Srinivas Iyengar rightly puts it, "Relations is an even mature achievement, and is something of a

bridge spanning childhood and age, and India and America." (Indian Writings in English, pp. 672)

Family is central in the social structure of Indian life. And peculiarity of it is its join nature having two types – matrimonial as well as patrimonial. Mother is the central and main authority in the matrimonial family system which is found in a few States in India and Patrimonial system provides central authority to the father which is found elsewhere. In a large Hindu family, there is a small colony living together. The Mother has the highest place in it and at the same time, it is dependent on the Father for guidance and at the same time, it is dependent on the father for guidance and instructions. Ramanujan's views towards his family are traditional and typically Indian. In the poems

about familial relations he asserts the same attitude.

In the poems 'A Wobbly Top' and 'Obituary', a father-son relationship is revealed which is further referred in the poem 'Entries for a Catalogue Fears'. In 'Obituary', poet describes the whole event of his father's death and the last lines:

'and he left us
a changed mother
and more than
one annual ritual. (Ibid, pp. 56)

His 'changed mother' is a widow wearing white saris, scorning ornaments, perfums and vermilion marks on her forehead and on the head. The 'change' in the mother is not only outward but she is changed inwardly, too because in Hindu families, woman's sole existence depends upon her husband's existence. She doesn't have individual identity.

In the poem, 'Of Mothers, Among other Things' the poet's deep attachment as well as the delicate relationship to his mother is pointed out. His mother is an old, thin lady wearing typical earrings with three diamonds. He has seen her running towards home in rain, for her children.

'..... her hands are a wet eagle's
two black – pink – crinkled feet.'
(Ibid, pp.5)

The awareness of the past makes her pick the grains on the floor. Poet's words freeze when he sees:

'her four
still fingers slowly flex
to pick a grain of rice from the
kitchen floor. (Ibid, pp.5)

It shows that the feeling for mother is Timeless. In the Modern age, this affection is perpetual from both sides with some exceptions. In the poem, 'History', the death of his great aunt is reported to him by his mother that when all the kith and kin were working in the kitchen, the little aunt with her two daughters 'alternately picked

their mother's body clean, -- unknown each to the other.' They picked

'of diamond ear-rings,
bangles, anklets, the pin
in her hair,
the toe rings from her wedding.'

(Ibid, pp 52)

The lack of affection in the little aunt for her sister and in daughters for their mother is caused by alienation in the adulthood as they think themselves to heir to her property.

'Love Poem for a Wife- 1' and 'Love Poem for a Wife- 2' are companion poems which discuss the most intimate relationship in married life, that exists between husband and wife he links that the major cause of the estrangement between them is their 'unshared childhood.' When poet's cousins meet in U.S.A., the gossiping prevails till midnight. His wife feels interested in his past life. She tries to recognize him in the album. She is surprised to see his

"father in a turban,
Mother standing on her bare
Splayed feet, silver rings
On he second toes". (Ibid, pp. 9)

The poet envies her past, her village dog-ride and mythological stories of the seven crazy aunts.

He knows that her father had become irrevocable by the age. But, he never liked to be reminded of the night when her father paced to and fro in the balcony anxiously waiting for his daughter who had gone out on a date with a Muslim. He strongly feels alienated when she quarrels with her brother James on the location of a bathroom. For this alienation, he suggests a solution that

'foretelling separate horoscopes
and mothers first periods,
and wed us in the oral cradle
and carry marriage back into
the namelessness of childhood.'

(Ibid, pp.11)

The clashes, the cause of alienation, are between traditionalism and modernism represented by himself and his wife.

‘Routine Day Sonnet’ adds to the feelings of alienation from his wife as he says:

‘..... I wake up with a start
To hear my wife cry her heart
Out as if from a crater
In hell: she hates me, I hate her,
I am a filthy rat and a satyr’(Ibid, pp.12)

In the ‘Love Poem for a Wife- 2’, this alienation is converted into affection. In a visit to India, various expressions pass on her face when she watches the emerald wilderness of Kerala the forests of rubber plants, and pepper vine. To her the cousins look like mythic men. As an outsider, that beautiful atmosphere turns into Aden where fierce Arabs are ready to stab, betray and whip. But, he tries to overcome this situation and dreams that his face has been changed to hers by losing his past. He looks in the mirror to see the reality and becomes happy because he attains the:

‘whole in the ambivalence
Of being half woman half
Man contained in a common body,
Androgynous as a god
Balancing stillness in the middle
of a duel to make it dance.’

(Ibid, pp. 28-29)

In ‘Small Scale Reflections ON a Great House’, poet portrays the picture of Indian Culture in rural India. In an Indian Hindu family, every daughter leaves her parent’s house and goes to her husband’s house forever. But, in the great house, they do go because the sons-in-law live there under the excuse of checking accounts of the house or teaching their nieces. And sometimes,

‘daughters
Get married to short-lived idiots.’

(Ibid, pp.42)

And come back as widows with their children. The daughters-in-law are trained to live inside the house because of ‘Paradah system is still alive in India. They are accustomed to waiting for and yielding to the favorable times or the monsoons, in their lives.

His deep love for his daughter is expressed in the poem, ‘Entries for the catalogue of fears’. As a father, he is afraid of any mishap about her because in the social picture of U.S.A.,

“the men in line
behind my daughter”. (Ibid, pp.30)

Relations is full of such instances in which A.K.Ramanujan tries prortray a vivid picture of women in Indian culture, society as he has experienced in his early stay in India and the same picture relocated in the context of the foreign culture. He finds some of the aspects to be great because of their depth in the Indian Philosophy. But, at the same time, he finds some traditions, costoms to be ridiculous and heartless. He also puts a picture of a “Ardhanari Nateshwara” which is a combination of half man and half woman.

His world of Indian family contains his own personal world seen from distance, women in kinships, social status of women in India contrasted to that of in U.S.A. where apart from freedom, there are the aspects like dating, insecurity, etc... he has effectively portayed the details in his poems in Relations.

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